

Stock Market Prediction by Regression Model with Social Moods

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Abstract : This paper presents a regression model with autocorrelated errors in which the inputs are social moods obtained by analyzing the adjectives in Twitter posts using a document topic model. The regression model predicts Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJIA) more precisely than autoregressive moving-average models.

Keywords : stock market prediction, social moods, regression model, DJIA

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